

1 **Title**

2 **An Environmental Health Vocabulary and its Semi-Automated Curation Workflow**

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47 The data that support this work are openly available in HAWC [Health Assessment Workspace](#)
48 [Collaborative \(HAWC\) \(epa.gov\)](#) and github repo [GitHub - USEPA/ehv: A repository for curation and](#)
49 [related activities of the Environmental Health Vocabulary \(EHV\)](#). The Environmental Health Vocabulary is
50 available at: <https://hawc.epa.gov/vocab/ehv/>.

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58 **Abstract**

59 **Background:** The environmental health vocabulary (EHV) represents manually curated terminologies
60 developed by the US Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Chemical Pollutant Assessment Division
61 (CPAD) for standardizing reporting of health effect information. Recognizing that manual data curation is
62 a resource bottleneck, a semi-automated curation workflow was realized.

63 **Objectives:** The objectives of this work are to describe the manual creation of the EHV and improve the
64 efficiency of manual data curation by implementing a new semi-automated curation workflow that
65 minimizes manual review using a sequence of computational text analysis and quality assurance (QA)
66 steps with a high level of accuracy.

67 **Methods:** To facilitate semi-automated curation a sequence of computational text analysis and manual
68 steps were developed. Described are 1) a series of computational text processing steps to normalize and
69 match extracted terms to the EHV, 2) a QA step of the computationally identified matches; 3) a manual
70 review of unmatched terms; and 4) curation of the EHV that includes completion of missing hierarchical
71 data and related metadata.

72 **Discussion:** The EHV was manually created to promote data aggregation, integration, accessibility and
73 transparent data exchange across EPA partners by normalizing the data extracted into the EPA Health
74 Assessment Workplace Collaborative (HAWC). The workflow described here removes the manual
75 curation bottleneck by transforming data curation into a streamlined semi-automated process powered
76 by computational text processing steps. This semi-automated curation method offers several
77 advantages to the environmental health community including (but not limited to) efficiency by
78 automating repeating data management tasks, scalability to a large volume of terms and terminology
79 resources, and better integration with other data sets and artificial intelligence (AI) and machine
80 learning (ML) models.

81 **Introduction**

82 The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency’s (EPA) Chemical Pollutant Assessment Division
83 (CPAD) utilizes systemic search, selection, and coding strategies to produce searchable databases of
84 study data. These databases include data and descriptive metadata that helps the reader evaluate the
85 reliability and quality of the evidence used in human health chemical assessment. The U.S. EPA has been
86 summarizing these data using data extraction templates, such as those implemented in systematic
87 evidence maps (SEMs) (Thayer et. al., 2022). Data extraction templates promote consistency across the
88 extracted study data and foster data accessibility and exchange across the environmental health
89 community. SEMs developed from these templates expedite the assessment process, can be defined as
90 “A comprehensive summary of the characteristics and availability of evidence as it relates to broader
91 themes of policy or decision-making relevance” (Wolffe et. al., 2019) without presenting conclusions on
92 the science supporting human health and environmental assessments. Increased utilization of template
93 formats streamlines data exchange and promote efficiencies and cost savings for all partners invested in
94 data gathering, problem formulation, and evidence surveillance. Yet, data extraction and reporting are
95 resource intensive due to the lack of structure and semantic variability in the reported data.

96 Data extraction is implemented in the U.S. EPA’s version of Health Assessment Workplace
97 Collaborative (HAWC) (<https://hawcprd.epa.gov/portal/>) as described in the U.S. EPA IRIS Handbook
98 (U.S. EPA, 2022). Part of the data extraction strategy includes application of agreed (meta)data
99 standards as proactive solutions to normalize and standardize the complex terminologies used to
100 describe the environmental health science domain. For example, there are many textual descriptions
101 data extractors could use to report the study details and findings for a particular finding or health effect
102 (e.g. alanine transferase ~ Serum Glutamate-Pyruvate Transaminase ~ Alanine Aminotransferase ~
103 Serum Glutamic-Pyruvic Transaminase ~ Alanine Transaminase ~ serum glutamate pyruvate
104 transaminase). While these are related, they do not match, leading to inconsistencies that, if not
105 standardized, complicate aggregation and integration of the findings linked within and across chemical
106 assessments and other human and environmental health data.

107 Therefore, the Environmental Health Vocabulary (EHV) was created by EPA CPAD in 2022 to
108 both normalize the reported terminology and standardize endpoint terms extracted into HAWC.
109 Standardization of the “Endpoint” field (meta)data is a significant semantic challenge because the
110 number of available endpoints is vast and, as described above, there are usually multiple ways to
111 describe the term. The EHV is a standardized and controlled vocabulary for reporting animal health
112 effects of environmental chemical exposure. A controlled vocabulary is an organized collection of words

113 and phrases that typically includes preferred terms that are non-redundant, unambiguous, can be
114 indexed, are machine readable and can be used to search a content management system through query
115 (see <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/programs/ehlc/resources> for additional information and
116 resources). The EHV is designed to have a five-tier hierarchical order such that: system->organ->effect-
117 >effect subtype->endpoint/outcome (Figure 1A). The hierarchy supports aggregation of endpoints into
118 visual representations that can be categorized at the system, organ, effect, or effect subtype level
119 depending on assessment need. The EHV can be used as a reference for reporting health effect
120 information primarily from animal bioassay studies and is currently implemented in HAWC. The EHV is
121 user enabled and accessible in the HAWC data entry screen where EHV terms are available for selection
122 by name or unique ID.

123 The EHV was developed through a manual curation effort of terms and phrases extracted from
124 the peer-reviewed animal toxicology literature (identified during assessment developed based on
125 Population, Exposure, Comparator, and Outcome criteria, PECO) into HAWC as part of the chemical
126 assessment workflow (see Chapter 5. Extraction and Display of results from epidemiological and
127 toxicological studies, U.S. EPA. 2022). In the current [EHV](#), the curation process consisted of 100% manual
128 review of the terms extracted into HAWC by PhD level experts with assessment development
129 experience. The manual process involved download of HAWC extracted terms, manual review
130 supplemented by consultation with domain experts as needed, look-up from terminology resources
131 such as Clinical Data Interchange Standard for Exchange of Nonclinical Data (CDISC SEND, 2023)
132 Controlled Terminology, Unified Medical Language Syntax (UMLS, 2023), and (Makris et. al., 2009) for
133 developmental and reproductive outcomes and comparison to prior health endpoint mappings from the
134 U.S. EPA's Integrated Science Assessments. As described above, the exact organization of the EHV and
135 terms within the EHV were developed to improve the efficiency of data aggregation, integration, and
136 filtering for visualization of the findings that support animal evidence synthesis and visualization in
137 human and environmental health assessments. For example, the EHV enables data aggregation and
138 visualization across multiple studies by health system, organ, and endpoint (Figure 1B). The EHV is
139 optional, allowing for free text data entry when a newly extracted term is not available in the EHV.
140 Approximately half of all public EPA HAWC projects are using the EHV, and within EHV enabled projects,
141 approximately 37,000 endpoints were extracted (last updated December 2024). Of those, approximately
142 70% of all endpoints used the EHV directly, with 30% using custom user defined terms.

143 Manual curation is a time-consuming data extraction process requiring expert technical insight.
144 Therefore, the objective of the EHV Curation Workflow described herein is to minimize the requirement

145 of manual review and analysis of extracted terms by applying a sequence of computational text analysis
146 steps with a high level of accuracy. Further, several steps in the curation workflow (term matching and
147 look-up) include text mining steps can be scaled-up and semi-automated using computational
148 approaches to streamline the data extraction process.

149 **Methodology**

150 **Workflow Overview**

151 The following terms associated with the
152 workflow described here are defined in Box 1: Term,
153 curate, standardize (or normalize), match (matching),
154 and cleanup. Terms without a confirmed match are
155 candidates for further manual review and possible
156 addition to the EHV.

157 Because terms in the EHV are organized within
158 a five-level hierarchy (i.e., organ system, organ, effect,
159 sub-effect, and endpoint), curation involves normalizing
160 the endpoint terms and then the associated terms
161 falling into each of the other four hierarchical levels.
162 Curation also involves completing missing definitions
163 and other metadata using Unified Medical Language
164 System (UMLS), Clinical Data Interchange Standards
165 Consortium - Standard Exchange for Nonclinical Data
166 (CDISC-SEND), Medical Subject Headings (MeSH),
167 Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
168 (LOINC), Uber-anatomy ontology (UBERON), etc.

169 The EHV curation workflow is intended to semi-
170 automate curation steps while including a human in the
171 loop. Terms are initially processed and grouped based
172 on whether the term is a new or existing term. The
173 specific details and subsequent steps of the workflow are described below.

174 At high level, the workflow compares terms extracted into HAWC to the existing EHV and sorts
175 them through the workflow depending on if they match or do not match the EHV. Terms that do not
176 match are candidates for additional curation and possible addition to the EHV. Terms extracted into

Box 1: Useful Definitions

Term – A word, phrase, or variant representing something specific and presented as a single datapoint. For this project, terms are health endpoint names.

Curate – To process a dataset of terms by removing extraneous terms or records, normalizing inconsistencies among datapoints within a single field, and adding or correcting required datapoints, identifiers, or metadata.

Standardize (or normalize) – To reduce an array of terms that all represent the same thing or concept to a single representative term that is used preferentially.

Match (matching) – Computationally or manually determining that a term is equivalent in meaning to a standardized term or that a term can be associated with an established corresponding identifier (ID).

Cleanup – Computationally or manually removing extraneous spaces, characters, or punctuation from a collection of terms.

177 HAWC are identified as matches if the exact term is already in the EHV or if the EHV has a synonym,
178 another term, or phrase that represents the same concept. Any synonymous matching terms and
179 phrases can be used to refine the efficiency of the workflow when applied to future sets of extracted
180 terms. These terms are compiled into a “cumulative equivalents dataset”. Matching terms enter QA/QC.
181 Terms that do not match the EHV after the computational text processing step proceed to manual and
182 manual review before QA/QC.

183 Figure 2 provides an overview of the EHV Curation Workflow for terms extracted into HAWC.
184 The workflow begins on the left with a set of HAWC extracted terms .

185 The workflow includes four distinct stages:

- 186 1. **Computational text processing** to clean-up extracted terms (e.g., remove punctuation and
187 extraneous characters) and identify matches to existing EHV terms.
- 188 2. **QA of the computationally identified matches**, including the use of hierarchical data to aid in
189 binning terms and manual QA review.
- 190 3. **Manual review and matching** of unmatched terms to identify additional matches that were not
191 identified by computational processing.
- 192 4. **Curation of EHV data**, including the normalization of terms and completion of hierarchical data
193 and metadata.

194 Each of these stages are discussed in more detail in the sections below.

195 **Computational Processing**

196 The computational processing stage within the workflow is shown in Figure 1 by the yellow
197 rectangular boxes. As the name implies, computational processing is carried out with a series of Python
198 scripts available in the GitHub Repo. To run these specific scripts without modification, the input data
199 must be formatted consistently .

200 Four steps are carried out within this stage:

- 201 • Text pre-processing
- 202 • Exact string matching
- 203 • Rules based matching; and
- 204 • SciSpacy (Neuman et. al., 2019), a Python package containing spaCy (<https://spacy.io/> models
205 for processing biomedical, scientific or clinical text entity matching.

206 All steps are applied to terms extracted into HAWC and input into a consistent file format. Note that
207 MS Excel is the file type used in this workflow so any change in file type will require update to the
208 scripts). Each of the scripts uses the [pandas](#) (V2.2.3) Python library to read the Excel information as a

209 data frame. Several functions are written in each of the scripts that can be applied to a column using
 210 panda’s “apply” method. Other scripts may be written as loops that utilize panda’s itterows method of
 211 iterating. To rerun the scripts, a user supplies the data files (the terms extracted into HAWC and the EHV
 212 inputs as MS Excel spreadsheets) and updates the scripts to the correct file paths to the data file(s).
 213 (Note that example data files are provided in the GitHub repo.) The column names need to match the
 214 original column names or be updated throughout the script. When data are transformed by the scripts,
 215 the resulting text is copied to a new column so that the original and transformed data can be viewed
 216 side-by-side for documentation and QA.

217 **Text Pre-Processing**

218 The goal of text pre-processing is to enhance the machine readability of the extracted terms for the
 219 subsequent steps. That is, the terms are “cleaned up” to improve the efficiency with which they can be
 220 matched to the EHV. The pre-processing code applies distinct transformations to achieve this goal:

- 221 • Numeric codes at the end of a string, often starting with "XXX" or numbers alone, are removed.
- 222 • Punctuation is separated from text characters by adding spaces before and after each
 223 punctuation character. Dashes or hyphens within the text are replaced with spaces.
- 224 • Leading and trailing spaces (i.e., spaces preceding and following the text, respectively) are
 225 removed and extraneous spaces within the text are replaced with a single space.
- 226 • All text characters are converted to lowercase to avoid case-related discrepancies during
 227 matching.
- 228 • Parentheses and brackets are removed, along with their contents, to minimize extraneous
 229 information that may interfere with matching.
- 230 • Words are lemmatized, i.e., reduced to their base form.

231 The resulting cleaned text is stored in the "1_cleaned" column of the Excel dataset. Specific
 232 examples for of text preprocessing of the terms “Alanine Aminotransferase”, “Excitation”, and “Live
 233 Fetuses/ Litter” are given in Table 1.

234 **Table 1. Text Preprocessing of HAWC Extracted Terms**

HAWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed
HAWC_ID	name	1_cleaned
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase
1570	Excitation	excitation
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter

235

236 **Exact String Matching**

237 After pre-processing, the exact string-check step searches for an exact match in the EHV for
 238 each HAWC extracted term. This step uses the endpoint terms only; hierarchical data, definitions or
 239 other contextual information is not used. Results are stored in the “EHV_ID” and “Endpoint” columns.
 240 When a match is identified, the EHV ID and Endpoint name are added to the “EHV_ID” and “Endpoint”
 241 columns, respectively. term is added into the original Excel file as shown in Table 2 (note that if there is
 242 no match the entry will be blank).

243 **Table 2. Text Preprocessing and Exact String Matching**

AWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching	
HAWC_ID	Name	1_cleaned	EHV_ID	Endpoint
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation		
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses/ Litter

244

245 **Rules-based Matching**

246 The rules-based matching step uses text analysis algorithms to identify matching endpoint terms
 247 when the HAWC extracted terms do not match the EHV term. The algorithms find matches by evaluating
 248 specific words or phrases and synonyms of those words and phrases. Extracted terms are matched to
 249 synonymous terms identified with the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK, V3.9.1) Python library (Bird et.
 250 al., 2009). Via a separate script, synonyms for individual words and phrases are obtained using functions
 251 in NLTK through its WordNet module, which is based on a database of English words and conceptual
 252 relationships between words such as antonyms and synonyms. Synonyms identified by NLTK resources
 253 are exported as a Python dictionary for use in rules-based matching. The script then searches for
 254 matches between words as well as between words and their synonyms. When a match is found (either
 255 exact match or through a synonym), the EHV ID and Endpoint name are added to the columns “EHV_ID”
 256 and “Endpoint”, respectively. Table 2 shows the results of the rules-based matching of HAWC extracted
 257 terms. If no match is found the cell is blank.

258 **Table 2. Text Preprocessing , Exact String Matching, and Rules-Based Matching of HAWC Extracted**
 259 **Terms**

AWC Extracted Term	Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching	Rules Based Matching
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HAWC_ID	Name	1_cleaned	EHV_ID	Endpoint	EHV_ID	Endpoint
7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation			3213	Inflammation
152	Live Fetuses/ Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses / Litter		

260

261 **SciSpacy Entity Matching**

262 The final step of the Computational Processing stage of the workflow leverages the capabilities
263 of SciSpacy, an open-source software library for advanced natural language processing. SciSpacy is
264 specifically adapted for the analysis of scientific and biomedical text sources (Neuman et.al., 2019).
265 Within the workflow, SciSpacy is used to link the terms in each dataset (i.e., terms extracted into HAWC
266 and EHV terms) to equivalent scientific entities (i.e., concepts). The objective of this step is to map the
267 identified entities within the text to their corresponding Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs) from the
268 Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) Metathesaurus (Bodenreider, O. 2004). The UMLS
269 Metathesaurus is a comprehensive source of biomedical and health-related concepts, terms, and codes.
270 The "SciSpacy" library employs sophisticated natural language processing techniques to recognize
271 entities within the text that are relevant to the concepts in the biomedical domain. These entities could
272 include medical terms, diseases, drugs, or anatomical structures. Once identified, the library links these
273 entities to specific Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs) within the UMLS Metathesaurus, providing a
274 standardized way to represent and reference biomedical concepts. Table 3 shows the results of the
275 SciSpacy of HAWC extracted terms. If no match is found the cell is blank. The full results of
276 computational data processing are available in the GitHub repo.

277 **Table 3. Text Preprocessing , Exact String Matching, Rules-Based Matching, and SciSpacy of HAWC**
278 **Extracted Terms**

AWC Extracted Term		Text Preprocessed	Exact String Matching		Rules Based Matching		SciSpacy	
HAWC _ID	name	1_cleaned	EHV_ ID	Endpoint	EHV_ ID	Endpoint	EHV_ ID	Endpoint

7713	Alanine Aminotransferase	alanine aminotransferase	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) 971	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) 971	2317	Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)
1570	Excitation	excitation			3213	Inflammation 3360		
152	Live Fetuses/Litter	live fetuses / litter	1740	Live Fetuses/Litter			1740	Live Pups Born

279 **QA/QC of Computational Matches**

280 Outputs from the computational processing stage include terms that matched the EHV and
281 terms that do not match. Terms that match the EHV proceed into the QC stage of the EHV Curation
282 Workflow. The purpose of this stage is to provide quality assurance (QA/QC) for the computational
283 matching of the extracted terms to EHV terms. This QA/QC only pertains to terms that have been
284 identified as matches by the computational processing steps. Terms that were not identified
285 computationally as matches proceed to full manual review and are evaluated in a separate sequence of
286 steps that is described under the “Manual Review and Matching” section below.

287 Because hundreds or thousands of extracted terms may be processed through the workflow at
288 once, the QA/QC review of individual terms can be time consuming. Therefore, to minimize the
289 resources required to perform QA/QC, the hierarchical data associated with each of the terms are used
290 to further evaluate the likelihood of correct matching. The inclusion of hierarchical data enables the
291 terms to be sorted into four groups (i.e., “bins”, Figure 3). Bin 1 represents instances where hierarchical
292 data are complete and all data matches. Bin 2 represents instances where all data matched, but
293 hierarchical data are incomplete. With this approach, partial QA/QC can be performed for bins 1 and 2
294 (all data match) whereas full review is required for bins 3 and 4 (data mismatch). This approach
295 minimizes the overall level of effort required for expert-level resources required for manual QA/QC.

296 Hierarchical data are compared and binned electronically based on two factors: (1) whether
297 complete hierarchical data are available for the potential term matches and (2) whether the available
298 hierarchical data match. Hierarchical data are complete only if data are available for all five levels (i.e.,
299 system, organ, effect, sub-effect, and endpoint) in both the EHV and HAWC extracted terms datasets.

300 The EHV and HAWC extracted term datasets are compared electronically and classified as true
301 (matching) or false (non-matching). The true/false classifications are written into the Excel dataset as a
302 new column named “Stg# Match as true (1) of false (0) to aid reviewers in sorting and prioritizing
303 records for QA review. During development of this workflow, it was observed that a majority of the

304 terms fell into bins 1 (all data match and hierarchical data were complete) and 3 (data mismatch, but
 305 hierarchical data were complete). It was also observed that the data mismatches were mostly due to
 306 transposition of hierarchical data fields. For example, effects and sub-effects were often swapped,
 307 causing a mismatch. Therefore, the current matching approach ignores the order of the hierarchical
 308 levels when evaluating matches. For these bin 3 instances, the assumption is that the hierarchical levels
 309 in the EHV are correct. However, QA/QC reviewers should record recommendations to reorder the EHV
 310 hierarchical data when appropriate.

311 For the most confidently matched terms in Bins 1 and 2, a single reviewer will review a random
 312 sample representing 10 percent of the matched terms. Discrepancies identified by the first reviewer will
 313 be reviewed and resolved by a secondary reviewer. If discrepancies are found in more than 25 percent
 314 of the high confidence terms sampled, the review steps will be repeated for a second, non-overlapping
 315 10 percent sample of the terms. This approach will be repeated until fewer than 5 percent of the terms
 316 are identified as discrepancies between reviewers. Based on the performance of the computational text
 317 in full scale implementation of the workflow, the proposed QA/QC schema may be adjusted to
 318 appropriately balance quality control and the level of effort required for manual review. A similar
 319 approach will be used for the less confidently matched terms in bins 3 and 4 except the reviewer will
 320 review 20 percent of the terms Computationally Matched to the EHV. If discrepancies arise during
 321 QA/QC that cannot be resolved by the primary and secondary reviewers, those terms will be classified as
 322 ambiguous and will proceed to expert manual review.

323 **TABLE 4. PROPOSED SCHEMA FOR MANUAL EXPERT QA/QC OF COMPUTATIONALLY MATCHED TERMS**

Bin	Hierarchical Data are Complete?	Hierarchical Data Match?	Matching Confidence	QA/QC Requirement
Bin 1	Yes	Yes	Higher confidence – Less manual review needed	10% by single reviewer; discrepancies resolved with second reviewer; repeat if >5% discrepancies
Bin 2	No	Yes		
Bin 3	Yes	No	Lower confidence – More manual review needed	20% by single reviewer; discrepancies resolved with second reviewer; repeat if >5% discrepancies
Bin 4	No	No		

324

325 **Manual Review and Matching**

326 The manual review and matching stage in the EHV curation workflow (Figure 1) apply to terms
327 where computational processing did not result in any matches to existing EHV terms. Whereas QA/QC
328 review described in the previous section compares paired sets of terms and hierarchical data to confirm
329 matches, the purpose of manual review in this stage is to identify matches those computational
330 methods failed to identify. To do this, expert reviewers compare 100 percent of the unmatched
331 extracted terms to the EHV. The reviewers decide whether each extracted term matches an existing EHV
332 term, has no match, or has inadequate data to support a decision (i.e., ambiguous). Extracted terms that
333 the reviewers determine do not match any existing EHV terms will be considered as candidates for
334 addition to the EHV.

335 When performing manual review and matching, expert reviewers will compare terms as well as
336 the hierarchical data associated with the EHV and extracted terms, as available. Comparing the
337 hierarchical data provides the expert reviewers with additional context to assess whether the endpoint
338 terms represent the same concept. For example, nearly equivalent terms will be considered
339 nonmatching if they are associated with different organs or organ systems in the EHV and extracted
340 term datasets. In addition, expert reviewers can filter the EHV data by hierarchical data fields to search
341 for matches more efficiently. If an extracted term is associated with a particular hierarchical category
342 (e.g., cardiovascular system), the reviewer can filter the EHV terms so that only cardiovascular endpoints
343 are shown for comparison. To increase the efficiency of this step, an electronic reviewer form or other
344 tool may be developed or adopted in the future to facilitate filtering and side-by-side data comparisons.

345 This manual review and matching stage will require expert knowledge of toxicological studies,
346 including study and exposure design, study methodology, human and animal physiology, and
347 toxicological health endpoints. Therefore, manual review will be based on domain expert judgement
348 due to incomplete hierarchical data, text and conceptual ambiguities, and other data limitations. The
349 basis for expert judgments will be documented by reviewers as explanatory comments when
350 appropriate to make transparent the rationale for reviewer decisions in a suitable ontology
351 management software.

352 For quality control, it may be advisable to require independent review of the matching decisions
353 by a second expert reviewer. The QA/QC approach, scope, and level of review should be decided
354 following a preliminary (e.g., spot-check) review of the initial matching and QA/QC results, including the
355 reviewer comments, the number of terms in the data set, and other factors. For example, depending on

356 the results of the preliminary review, full QA/QC of the expert review could require a second,
357 independent review of all terms, secondary review of a sample of terms, or secondary review focused
358 on matched terms, non-matched terms, or terms considered inconclusive by the primary reviewer.
359 Discrepancies between the primary and secondary reviewers should be resolved by a third reviewer.

360 The EHV Curation Workflow sorts HAWC extracted terms into two groups, including terms found
361 to have matches already in the EHV and terms determined to be absent from the EHV. The process for
362 curating these term groups to maintain the EHV is discussed below.

363 **Terms With EHV Matches**

364 A primary objective of the EHV Curation Workflow is to identify health endpoints that can be
365 added to the EHV. As shown in Figure 2, terms that are matched to EHV terms follow the pipeline to
366 curate hierarchical data and metadata. Terms that are already represented in the EHV are excluded from
367 further consideration, although these terms and associated hierarchical data are useful to consider for
368 refining the EHV. In the EHV curation steps, the hierarchical and other data associated with the matching
369 extracted terms can be used to complete EHV information for the existing terms. A detailed sub
370 workflow for this step has not yet been developed, but this sub workflow is expected to reference
371 existing resources such as the UMLS for missing information. Missing information may include endpoint
372 terms that lack complete hierarchical data, definitions, and identifiers such as UMLS concept unique
373 identifiers (CUI) and/or unique identifiers of semantic types (TUI), when available. As indicated by the
374 dashed line in Figure 2, the sub workflow would apply for curating hierarchical data and metadata to
375 existing EHV terms that were not matched to any of the extracted terms that entered the workflow.

376 The continued curation of EHV matching terms could be used to refine the efficiency of the
377 computational processing stage of the workflow. Specifically, new equivalent terms may be identified
378 from the EHV matching terms, which can be added to the cumulative equivalents dataset library. With
379 each application of the EHV Curation Workflow, extracted terms determined to equate to existing EHV
380 endpoints, along with their associated data and EHV counterparts, are added to this cumulative
381 equivalents dataset. In subsequent applications of the workflow, the rules-based script will compare
382 extracted terms entering the workflow to the cumulative equivalents dataset to find EHV matches that
383 were identified by previous application of the workflow to sets of extracted terms. This approach may
384 incrementally increase the efficiency and confidence of semi-automated, rules-based matching when
385 the workflow is applied to new sets of extracted terms. Rules-based matching using the cumulative
386 equivalents dataset has not yet been developed but could be added to the existing workflow as a
387 potential next step.

388 **Terms Without EHV Matches**

389 The EHV curation workflow employs a series of computational and manual steps to match
390 extracted terms to EHV endpoints. Terms that are unmatched after the completion of the workflow may
391 be potential new endpoints for addition to the EHV. As part of the expert review steps reviewers will
392 classify unmatched terms as either eligible health endpoints or ambiguous terms (e.g., not health
393 endpoints). Eligible endpoints recommended by the reviewers will undergo additional review to confirm
394 induction as new EHV endpoints.

395 As shown in Figure 2, the terms without EHV matches progress toward addition to the EHV via
396 the normalize terms step. Normalizing a new EHV term means selecting the precise word or phrase that
397 will be used to consistently represent the new health endpoint concept. Normalization may be needed if
398 there are various forms (i.e., plural or singular) of words or phrases that are commonly used to
399 represent the same concept (e.g., white blood cells, WBC, monocytes or alanine aminotransferase, ALT,
400 serum glutamic, pyruvic transaminase, SGPT). To promote interoperability among tools and datasets,
401 the UMLS and/or other relevant ontologies will be used to identify normalized terms and phrases, as
402 available. If normalized terms are not found in other relevant ontologies, the most appropriate form of
403 the term will be selected for use in the EHV.

404 **Challenges and limitations**

405 Currently implementation of the workflow is limited because some EHV endpoints are missing
406 metadata and/or definitions. For example, SciSpacy uses metadata and definitions to link endpoints to
407 biomedical ontologies and other knowledgebases (including UMLS). If these metadata and definitions
408 are missing, SciSpacy may fail to correctly identify correct terms. Further, missing metadata and
409 definitions provide context, that when missing, can lead to inaccuracies in linking relationships between
410 terms and in identifying correct concepts from probed knowledgebases. Through iterative curation of
411 the EHV, it is expected that these data gaps will lessen, increasing performance of the computational
412 text processing steps and increase efficiency by reducing the overall time needed for manual curation.
413 Therefore, a critical next step will include data gap filling (including hierarchical metadata and
414 definitions) of the current EHV.

415 The need for domain expertise is also a possible challenge to the workflow. Non-experts may
416 lack knowledge on the current standards and conventions in environmental health science and struggle
417 to accurately curate terms possibly leading to inconsistencies, data gaps, ambiguity, missing hierarchical
418 data, and or missing definitions. These inaccuracies could feedback on computational processing steps,
419 impeding performance or introducing inaccuracies that decrease trustworthiness and interoperability

420 with other terminology resources. Therefore, agreed upon data standards for vocabularies and
421 ontologies within a complex domain are proactive solutions that can be adopted by a community
422 working together to ensure consistency, quality, accessibility and exchange of data. The true challenge
423 will continue to be the continued curation of these metadata and maintenance of a pool of domain
424 experts as data sets and ontologies are developed. A decentralized model for data curation within a
425 trusted community of domain experts is needed to bridge knowledge gaps and may be achieved through
426 training, community building, tooling, and incentives.

427 **Next Steps**

428 Implementation of the EHV Curation Workflow is currently undergoing additional development
429 and testing to include automation tools using an ontology management software application. For this
430 use case the Graphite Taxonomy and Ontology Management system was selected as the software
431 application to manage both the source vocabulary as well as the curation. The ontology management
432 software is specific for ontologies and allows modeling from multiple terminology resources, capturing
433 provenance during curation while allowing terminology changes back to other software (such as HAWC)
434 after curation. Through implementation of the curation workflow, detailed sub workflows will be
435 developed for curation and standardization of hierarchical metadata for EHV terms. The metadata is
436 needed to improve the performance of some of the computational scripts (e.g. SciSpacy) that are
437 currently limited by lack of metadata such as term definitions that will additionally expand the
438 computational processing stage to match extracted terms using the cumulative equivalents dataset.
439 Anticipated improvements will also be realized as the ontology software should provide a user-friendly
440 interface for QA/QC that is web accessible, possibly allowing crowdsourcing and asynchronous
441 collaboration. Since the EHV is the language standard for reporting animal health effects information in
442 human health assessments conducted by EPA CPAD and is made publicly available as a download as well
443 as via the publicly available HAWC application, it is envisaged that the EHV can help to standardize the
444 way findings are reported across the environmental health community. We anticipate engaging with the
445 broader environmental health science community to ensure not only standardization of the language,
446 but also coverage of biomedical science and other knowledge domains reported in the literature, but
447 not yet covered by the EHV. The EHV is currently machine actionable meaning that it is “AI ready”. We
448 anticipate future updates to the curation workflow will incorporate generative AI to take a deeper dive
449 into the more specific topics that describe environmental health science.

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Figures

1a)

1b)

Figure 1A and B. A) The environmental Health Vocabulary (EHV) is a five-level hierarchy to describe health effects within assessments. Currently the EHV describes animal health effects. The only implementation of the EHV is within HAWC and is available at <https://haww.epa.gov/vocab/ehv>. B) The EHV enables a visual summary of endpoints aggregated by health system (hepatic) and organ (liver).

Figure 2

Figure 2. Environmental health vocabulary (EHV) curation workflow. The curation workflow is presented in stages that include computational text processing (preprocess text, exact string match, rules-based script, and SciSpacy), QA/QC of computational matches, manual review and matching followed by QA/QC, and curation of the EHV data.

1 Figure 3

2

3 Figure 3. QA of matching terms. Hierarchical data enable to terms to be sorted into four bins based
4 on the completeness of the hierarchical data and the data match/mismatch. Bins 1 and 2 receive a
5 partial review whereas bins 3 and 4 receive a more complete review.

6